

POSSIBILITIES OF GAME METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN SECONDARY SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7218831>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27th September 2022

Accepted: 10st October 2022

Online: 18TH October 2022

KEY WORDS

Game, physiological, methods, teaching, social, materials, training, subject, playing, technology.

ABSTRACT

In modern society, much attention is paid to the search for new forms, methods and techniques of teaching. The modern school needs such teaching methods that could not only teach qualitatively, but also reveal the personality of a person, his creative potential. Also, modern education should teach a person to adapt to modern life, teach him to make decisions quickly and correctly, and actively master situations of social change.

The main function of pedagogical activity is not just to transfer knowledge, but to create problem-cognitive situations and manage the process of students' cognitive activity.

A.S. Vygotsky and A.N. Leontiev identify three main types of human activity: labor, play and education. All these types are closely related to each other. According to many psychologists, the purpose of the game is the development and self-realization of students. Therefore, games are very firmly and actively included in didactics. The game has become not only an independent activity, but also its universal tool in almost all spheres of public life. Life situations are modeled in it, properties, qualities, states, skills; abilities necessary for the individual to perform social, professional and creative functions are fixed.

Game activity performs the following functions:

- entertaining (entertain, give pleasure, inspire, arouse interest);
- communicative (mastering the dialectic of communication);
- diagnostic (identification of deviations from normative behavior, self-knowledge during the game);
- game therapy (overcoming various difficulties arising in other types of life activity);
- self-realization (manifestation of abilities and hidden opportunities);
- socialization (inclusion in the system of public relations);
- aesthetic (pleasure that is experienced from the game).

In a modern school, gaming activity is used in the following cases:

As an independent method for mastering a particular topic;

Like elements, sometimes very essential, of some other method;

As a whole lesson or part of it (introduction, explanation, consolidation, control or exercise);

It is possible to use the game when organizing extra-curricular activities.

When using the game method of teaching, the task of the teacher is, first of all, to organize the cognitive activity of students, during which their abilities, especially creative ones, would develop.

The use of gaming forms of learning makes the educational process more meaningful and of higher quality, since:

- the game draws each student individually and all together into active cognitive activity and, thus, is an effective means of managing the educational process;
- learning in the game is carried out through the students' own activities, which are in the nature of a special type of practice, during which up to 90% of information is assimilated;
- game-free activity, giving the opportunity to choose, self-expression, self-determination and self-development for its participants;
- the game has a certain result and stimulates the student to achieve the goal and realize the way to achieve the goal;
- in the game, teams or individual students are initially equal (there are no bad and good students: there are only players); the result depends only on the player, his level of preparedness, abilities, endurance, skills, character;
- the impersonal learning process in the game acquires a personal meaning;
- competitiveness is attractive for students; the pleasure received from the game creates a comfortable state in the lessons of a foreign language and enhances the desire to study the subject;

- in the game there is a certain sacrament-undeceived answer, which activates the mental activity of the student, pushes him to search for an answer;

- the game occupies a special place in the system of active learning: it is synthetic, as it is both a method and a form of organization of learning, synthesizing in itself almost all methods of active learning.

The use of the game teaching method contributes to the implementation of important methodological tasks, such as:

- creation of psychological readiness of students for verbal communication;
- ensuring the natural need for repeated repetition of language material by them;
- training students in choosing the right speech option, which is a preparation for situational spontaneous speech in general.

By type of activity, the games are divided into:

- physical (motor);
- intellectual (mental);
- labor;
- social;
- psychological.

By the nature of the pedagogical process, the following groups of games are distinguished:

- teaching, training, controlling, summarizing;
- cognitive, educational, developing;
- reproductive, productive, creative;
- communicative, diagnostic, career guidance, psych technical;

According to the nature of the gaming technique, the game can be divided into:

- subject;
- plot;
- role-playing;
- business;
- imitation;
- Dramatization games.

Games can be grammatical, lexical, phonetic, spelling. All of them contribute to the formation of speech skills.

Mastering the grammatical material, first of all, creates an opportunity for the transition to active speech of students. The use of gaming learning methods will help make boring work more interesting and attractive. For example, a number of grammar games can be effective in introducing new material.

The technology of the game consists of the following stages:

1 stage of preparation (scenario development, drawing up a plan for the game, the general conduct of the game, the characteristic features of the characters);

2 explanation stage (introduction to the game, orientation of participants, determination of the mode of operation, formulation of the main goal of the lesson, justification for posing the problem and choosing the situation, working with texts, psychological preparation of students);

3 the stage of conducting (the process of the game);

4 stage of analysis and generalization (analysis, reflection, assessment and self-assessment of the work, conclusions and generalizations, recommendations).

In the learning process, four main types of dramatization are used: pantomime, improvisation, informal dramatization, formal dramatization. This technique should be reasonably combined with other traditional and non-traditional forms and methods of work, taking into account the objectives of the lesson, the characteristics of the study group, the content of the educational material. Elements of dramatization in the lesson can be used in teaching both reading and listening. Playing the role of a particular character

from fiction, while being emotionally appealing, has a stimulating effect on the performance of certain language operations in which the role is embodied. In a dramatized game, not only the vocabulary of students increases, but their attitude towards each other changes. The material for dramatization should correspond to the age, development, and interests of children. The most suitable material for children should be considered folk dramatic games, round dances and other songs with a dramatic element, children's dramatic games, simple dramas, the theme of which is various human activities; improvisation of everyday scenes so beloved by children (playing doctor, trading, etc.); finally, the free reproduction of familiar and favorite fairy tales (dramatization in the narrow sense of the word).

The use of various game techniques and situations in the classroom contributes to the formation of a friendly team in the classroom, since each student in the game has the opportunity to look at himself and his comrades from the outside. Role-playing games and the use of dramatization techniques bring up the responsibility and mutual assistance of students, since in the game they must be "one team", constantly helping and supporting each other. Ignorance of a certain vocabulary or grammar by one participant in the game will interfere with the successful course of this game, and all other participants will suffer from this. Therefore, with the competent organization of lessons by the teacher, the students will always prepare especially carefully, not wanting to let their comrades down.

The use of games at various levels of education not only helps in learning a

foreign language, but also plays a certain role in the transition of the student to a

new, higher level of mental development.

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